

DIAMAS

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

DIAMAS Synergy report

Deliverable 6.1

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Consortium overview

AMU	UNIVERSITÉ D'AIX MARSEILLE	FR
PVM	PROTISVALOR MEDITERRANEE SAS	FR
OPERAS	OPEN ACCESS IN THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA THROUGH SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION	BE
CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR
EIFL	STICHTING EIFL.NET	NL
FECYT	FUNDACIÓN ESPAÑOLA PARA LA CIENCIA Y LA TECNOLOGIA, F.S.P., FECYT	ES
TSV	TIETEELLISTEN SEURAIN VALTUUSKUNNASTA	FI
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
UB	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA	ES
UniZD	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZADRU	HR
FFZG	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZAGREBU FILOZOFSKI FAKULTET	HR
Science Europe	SCIENCE EUROPE	BE
EUA	ASSOCIATION EUROPÉENNE DE L'UNIVERSITÉ	BE
OASPA	STICHTING OPEN ACCESS SCHOLARLY PUBLISHERS ASSOCIATION	NL
UiT	UNIVERSITETET I TROMSØ - NORGES ARKTISKE UNIVERSITET	NO
CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT
UGOE	GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITÄT GÖTTINGEN STIFTUNG ÖFFENTLICHEN RECHTS	DE
SPE	STICHTING SPARC EUROPE	NL
UU	UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	NL
EKT	ETHNIKO KENTRO TEKMIRIOSIS KAI ILEKTRONIKOU PERIECHOMENOU	EL
IBL PAN	INSTYTUT BADAŃ LITERACKICH POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	PL
ESF	FONDATION EUROPÉENNE DE LA SCIENCE	FR
Jisc	Jisc LBG	UK
DOAJ	INFRASTRUCTURE SERVICES FOR OPEN ACCESS C I C	UK

Document overview

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Acronyms

ANR	French National Research Agency, Agence nationale de la recherche
CLACSO	Latin American Council of Social Sciences
CoNOSC	Council for National Open Science Coordination
DFG	German Research Foundation, Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional open Access publishing Models to Advance Scholarly communication
DOAS	Diamond OA Standard
EDCH	European Diamond Capacity Hub
EDIB	Equity, diversity, inclusion, and belonging
EQSIP	Extensible Quality Standard for Institutional Publishing
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
EUA	European Universities Association
FSD	Funders, Sponsors and Donors
IPSP	Institutional Publishers and Publishing Service Provider
OA	Open Access
OPERAS	Open scholarly communication in the European Research Area for social sciences and humanities
RHF	De regionale helseforetakene
RCN	Research Council of Norway
UAEM	Autonomous University of Mexico State
UÓR	Oscar Ribas University
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization

Executive Summary

This Synergy Report (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14719777>) is a deliverable for the DIAMAS Project (D6.1), funded by the European Union's Horizon WIDERA-2021-ERA-01 research and innovation programme; it provides background and context for an accompanying report: D6.2, "Recommendations and Implementation Guidelines for Institutions, Funders, Sponsors, and Donors, and Policymakers." Both this report and the recommendations have been informed by a series of workshops and consultation events, which are described as part of D6.2 ([10.5281/zenodo.14719790](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14719790)). The Synergy Report builds on the work of the other project work packages and deliverables and concludes with a call for stakeholders to work together to make Diamond OA a reality.

1.0 Introduction

The predominantly commercial approach to open access (OA) has raised urgent questions about its economic sustainability and the responsible use of taxpayers' money, while also introducing considerable inequities for authors in terms of access to funds for publication, as well as problems of research integrity such as paper mills, research fraud, and retractions. The scholarly publishing landscape has also become increasingly complex and diverse leading to a resetting of priorities where stakeholders are trying to rebalance the focus on the traditional large commercial publisher offering, to a more diverse set of publishing models and innovative ideas. Examples include the navigation of transformative agreements, article processing charges, self-archiving and rights retention (see The Budapest Open Access Initiative, 2022; Brayman *et al.*, 2024).

The drawbacks of commercial approaches to OA suggest that scholarly publishing may increasingly require a firmer degree of control by both public authorities and the academic community. Recently, Diamond Open Access (Diamond OA) has captured the attention of European public sector organisations and policymakers as an alternative to OA based on APCs and Transformative Agreements. 'Diamond OA' refers to a scholarly model of publication where publishers, journals, and platforms do not charge fees to either authors or readers, and where all content-related elements of publishing are directly controlled by the academic community and public institutions.

This evolution of scholarly publishing increasingly sees the case for a more equitable and inclusive publishing system through Diamond OA. At the institutional level, Diamond OA is often adopted as a model for institutional publishing. This relates to publishing activities by academic organisations that run, manage, fund, and promote scholarly communication through publishing services.

Within the European Research Area (ERA), Diamond OA has yet to become the central model for the dissemination of research findings. Nevertheless, Diamond OA is gaining momentum in Europe and beyond as a scholar-driven, inclusive, and equitable approach to disseminating research knowledge.

Diamond OA particularly flourishes in countries with strong community leadership and public funding. In some countries, such as Finland, France, Spain and Croatia, national journal

publishing is financially supported through public financing that aims to maintain a prosperous and locally relevant scholarly communication environment in the national languages; this is often realised through Diamond OA publishing. In countries where institutional publishers are coordinated at the national level, more public funding may also be available for Diamond OA (Taşkın, *et al.*, 2024).

The landscape of institutional publishing in Europe remains quite diverse. There are many institutional publishers and service providers of different shapes and sizes, with differing missions and offerings, that serve a range of disciplines. Funding models are similarly diverse. The sustainability of Diamond OA is largely dependent on institutional and other public funding to survive and thrive.

This Synergy Report is a deliverable for the DIAMAS Project (D6.1); it provides background and context for an accompanying report: D6.2, “Recommendations and Implementation Guidelines for Institutions, Funders, Sponsors, and Donors, and Policymakers.” Both this report and the recommendations have been informed by a series of workshops and consultation events, which are described as part of D6.2 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14719790>). The Synergy Report builds on the work of the other project work packages and deliverables. The report begins with a brief overview of the efforts in the last five years to give more visibility to Diamond OA before discussing the various reasons to support Diamond OA as an alternative to commercial publishing. We have used the data from previous DIAMAS reports to provide publisher typologies in order for key stakeholders to more easily identify publishing operations in their organisations. The report also contains a summary of key project outputs that are relevant to Institutions, Funders, Sponsors, and Donors (FSDs), and Policymakers. The report concludes with a call for stakeholders to work together to make Diamond OA a reality.

2.0 A brief history of institutional publishing and Diamond Open Access

Diamond OA is a scholarly communication model with a long history, particularly in Latin America. Today, Diamond OA counts for a significant proportion of OA publishing worldwide, and it is estimated that they make up 66% of journals in the Directory of Open Access Journals (Bosman *et al.*, 2021). However, until recently, the scope of this ecosystem remained largely out of sight and unexplored in the ERA, with the exception of Eastern Europe (Taşkın *et al.*, 2024).

The landmark *Diamond Open Access Journals Study* (J. Bosman *et al.*, 2021) first uncovered and made visible the vast size and scope of the ecosystem worldwide. In particular, the study was instrumental in revealing the extent of a wide archipelago of relatively small and isolated Diamond OA journals and platforms serving diverse scientific communities in different languages. Despite the richness of the Diamond OA landscape, findings from the study showed that this collaborative, community-driven publishing model

needs to be more efficiently organised, coordinated, and funded to better support researchers in disseminating their work. Challenges such as lack of technical capacity, management, visibility, and sustainability of journals and platforms need to be addressed in order to realise the vision of a just scholarly communication ecosystem. The European University Association (EUA) defines a just scholarly publishing ecosystem as an ecosystem "that is transparent, diverse, economically affordable and sustainable, technically interoperable, and steered by the research community and its institutions through coordinated policies" (EUA, 2022). The definition itself is inspired by the work of Science Europe (Philipp *et al.*, 2021) and by the International Science Council (2021).

Results collected through the DIAMAS Institutional Publishing Landscape Survey (Armengou *et al.*, 2023) provided further detail on the state of play of institutional publishing in Europe. The report investigated the work of 685 institutional publishers and publishing service providers (IPSPs) based in the ERA. The findings showed that institutional publishing and equitable, community-driven scholarly publishing are intrinsically connected, with a large number of respondents already operating with a Diamond OA model, employing open science practices and displaying high editorial standards and professionalism. Approximately 60% of the responding IPSPs are also part of "parent organisations", which are often institutions such as universities, other research performing organisations (RPOs) and learned societies. Parent organisations can provide a diverse set of services to the IPSPs, including infrastructure, financial support and the academic resources needed to maintain and operate Diamond OA journals and platforms. Nevertheless, these institutional publishers can be isolated and require further support to guarantee the sustainability of Diamond OA journals and platforms. They are challenged by the lack of sustainable funding and technical proficiency, the dependence on unpaid and voluntary work, as well as insufficient support at organisational, financial, legal and technical levels.

Both public sector engagement in and political support for Diamond OA have grown considerably in recent years. Public sector engagement is organised around the *Action Plan for Diamond Open Access* (Ancion *et al.*, 2022), which focuses on improving the efficiency, quality standards, capacity, and sustainability of this model. Launched in March 2022 by Science Europe, cOAlition S, OPERAS, and the French National Research Agency (ANR), the action plan has since been endorsed by more than 160 organisations and 150 individuals from across the research sector ([European Diamond Capacity Hub | EDCH](#)).

The Diamond OA community has been taking shape through a series of events. A first conference in September 2022 in Zadar, Croatia served to discuss Diamond OA as a not-for-profit scholarly communication model (Science Europe, 2022a). The endorsers of the action plan took a step forward with the *Global Summit on Diamond Open Access* in October 2023 in Toluca, Mexico (Redalyc, *et al.*, 2023). The summit was organised by a global consortium, including AmeliCA, Autonomous University of Mexico State (UAEM), cOAlition S, ANR, Latin American Council of Social Sciences (CLACSO), OPERAS, Oscar Ribas University (UÓR), Redalyc, Science Europe, and UNESCO. This emphasised the global outlook of the community, and focussed the discussion on the community-led and -owned nature of the model.

The [2nd Global Summit on Diamond Open Access](#) (University of Cape Town, *et al.*, 2024) took place in December 2024 in Cape Town, South Africa, and explored social justice as an

element of the model. Through the lens of social justice in scholarly communication, global perspectives were presented on framing scholarly knowledge as a public good, building sustainable open access infrastructure, creating innovations hubs, and reforming research assessment. The event was an important next step in ensuring equitable access to scholarly knowledge and fostering global collaboration.

Political support for Diamond OA has been growing in alignment with initiatives taken by the public research sector. At the global level, UNESCO is facilitating the Secretariat of a Global Alliance for Diamond Open Access as part of their engagement through the *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science* (UNESCO, 2021). UNESCO officially announced the Global Alliance for Diamond Open Access on 10 July 2024 (UNESCO, 2024), highlighting its vision, mission, and objectives, and engaging stakeholders in a collaborative effort to promote Diamond OA.

At a national level, governments are increasingly focussing on Diamond OA as the way forward for open scholarly communication. In Europe, political support for Diamond OA took a step forward with the Council of the European Union (EU) adopting *conclusions on high-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy, and equitable scholarly publishing* on 23 May 2023 (Council of the European Union, 2023). EU Member States in these conclusions unanimously support “the development of aligned institutional and funding policies and strategies regarding not-for-profit open access multi-format scholarly publishing models in Europe with no costs for authors or readers, and to set and implement roadmaps or action plans for a significant expansion of such publishing models.” Representative organisations of the public research sector in Europe welcomed these conclusions in a joint statement (EUA *et al.*, 2023).

Notable recent developments and commitments by research funders to Diamond OA include the French National Research Agency (ANR) committing €250,000 to fund the European Diamond Capacity Hub (Saenen *et al.*, 2024) and the German Research Foundation (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, DFG) inviting proposals for the establishment of a service centre to develop further and consolidate the Diamond OA landscape in Germany (DFG, 2024). The new action plan from the Bibsam Consortium in Sweden (2024) and the *Norwegian National Strategy for Scientific Publishing after 2024* (De regionale helseforetakene (RHF) *et al.*, 2023) make the recommendation to set up a Nordic Centre for Diamond OA. Various institutional and national stakeholders from Sweden, Finland, and Denmark, and Norway, including the Research Council of Norway (RCN) and Stockholm University Library, are currently exploring this option. Finally, Diamond OA was also discussed at The Council for National Open Science Coordination (CoNOSC) Members meeting in Bucharest in June 2024 (CoNOSC, 2022). Here, in the context of looking into the costs of OA legacy publishing, more equitable pathways to OA publishing through Diamond OA were discussed, including an update on DIAMAS research findings and considerations for how and what to fund. A discussion ensued amongst members who were keen to create a more financially sustainable scholarly communication system.

Collaboration between higher education institutions and research funders is vital for OA publishing actors to flourish and is a condition for Diamond OA. Unlike commercial publishers who rely on relatively stable resources from public and quasi-public institutions, funds external to the institution directed to the Diamond ecosystem often currently take the form of time-limited grants. The DIAMAS IPSP Sustainability Research Report (Brun *et al.*, 2024) strongly encourages national open science policymakers, their public institutions and RFOs to strategically invest in funds to invest in IPSP operations and innovate in the Diamond OA sector by developing new and existing services. These funds then need to be provided in ways that do not generate significant additional administrative labour and thus transform grants into financial burdens. In addition, publishing infrastructures play a crucial role in the Diamond OA ecosystem (e.g. Diamond OA journal and book hosting platforms, software, etc.) and it is paramount that public institutions and research funders help to fund the maintenance and operations of such infrastructures.

3.0 Why support Diamond Open Access?

Institutions, Funders, Sponsors and Donors (FSDs), and policymakers may have different reasons to support Diamond OA, stemming from their commitment to support both the research community and society at large. The goal is to provide the research community with an aligned, high-quality, and sustainable open scholarly communication ecosystem at a controllable cost.

Reasons to support Diamond OA generally fall into four main areas. First of all, funding Diamond OA ensures that public funding leads to cost-controlled public benefits for scholars, scientists, practitioners and society. Diamond OA publishing is scholar-led as opposed to profit-led. Since no fees are charged, there is no profit motive and no predatory behaviour. Secondly, Diamond OA is a more equitable and socially responsible form of scholarly publishing, creating bibliodiversity and preserving multilingualism. Third, Diamond OA is about keeping publishing autonomy in the hands of the scholarly community. Fourth, Diamond OA publications generally follow the same quality control mechanisms as other publications. The new Diamond OA Standard (DOAS) elaborated in the DIAMAS project sets strong quality standards for the future.

3.1 Positive research cultures

Research organisations and policymakers share a responsibility to strengthen positive research cultures (Science Europe, 2022b) that reflect core values such as autonomy, freedom, care, collegiality, collaboration, equality, diversity, inclusion, integrity, ethics, openness, and transparency. While these values are often implicit, supporting Diamond OA is a concrete way to affirm them. Journals, platforms, and repositories within this model are led and owned by scholarly communities and serve a diverse range of typically smaller, multilingual, and multicultural scholarly communities, reinforcing the principle of bibliodiversity. By its nature and design, Diamond OA promotes equity and inclusion in the creation and dissemination of scholarly knowledge. By its nature and design, Diamond OA content can be utilized as a global accessible multilingual corpus or multicultural training dataset for any computational methods including TDM and AI that can be fully used not only by commercial entities but also by the academy.

Regarding bibliodiversity, Diamond OA generally serves multilingual and multicultural scholarly communities (see Helsinki Initiative on Multilingualism in Scholarly Communication, 2019). In September 2024, the G20 Research and Innovation (R&I) Ministers agreed to encourage "the use of native languages in science", and facilitate "the dissemination of science in all languages" (European Commission, 2024). Research shows that it is more diverse in terms of the language of publications, with about three times as many Diamond OA articles published in a diversity of languages compared to gold open access (Pölonen, 2024).

Research integrity and quality are central to the scholarly publishing system, and Diamond OA contributes to upholding them. Diamond OA journals are directly controlled by the academic community and public institutions and do not charge fees to read or publish, so they are unlikely to prioritise quantity over quality of publications. Furthermore, the Diamond OA Standard (Consortium of the DIAMAS project, 2024a) provides Diamond OA publishers with a self-assessment tool (Consortium of the DIAMAS project, 2024b) and a common direction towards the highest standards of quality, transparency and integrity of scholarly communication.

3.2 Economic and financial responsibilities

Research organisations and policymakers must take economic and financial responsibilities to ensure that scholarly publishing is sustainable, cost-controlled and provides societal value. For public organisations, this is a key part of their fiduciary duty to ensure that public funds are optimally invested and lead to societal benefits. Diamond OA offers a sustainable funding model, characterised by cost transparency and control. Unlike profit-driven and extractive practices in other models, along with the large international society journals, Diamond OA is led and owned by scholarly communities. This approach ensures a better return on public investment, maximising the societal impact of research funding.

These economic and financial considerations are pertinent, particularly since Gold OA access and transformative agreements are proving to be far costlier than previously envisaged and that these models will not deliver a full OA transformation soon (Brayman *et al.*, 2024). Some national initiatives are concerned about the sustainability of these kinds of models and are therefore exploring how to embrace Diamond OA publishing more.¹

Diamond OA is expected to lead to a stabilisation of costs since it is accountable to and controlled by the scholarly community, whereas the costs of the current models are unpredictable and make it difficult to plan and budget. Cost can also be made more transparent and controllable without threatening any business or competition interests, as with commercial publishers.

¹ Ireland: <https://www.mdpi.com/2304-6775/12/3/19>; Germany <https://www.zbmed.de/en/research/current-projects/sedoa>; Scandinavian countries: <https://septentrio.uit.no/index.php/SCS/article/view/7881>; The Netherlands: <https://openjournals.nl/>

3.3 Dynamics of authority, patronage, and legitimacy

When supporting Diamond OA, research organisations and policymakers must take into account the dynamics of authority, patronage, and legitimacy. This includes both top-down support, such as political, financial, and logistical backing from national authorities and funding bodies, and bottom-up initiatives driven by universities, research institutions, and scholarly communities. In recent years, political support for Diamond OA has grown, particularly from European governments (Council of the European Union, 2023) and UNESCO (UNESCO, 2021). At the same time, research communities have called for collective action, as seen in their endorsement of the Action Plan for Diamond OA (Ancion et al., 2022).

The role of different publishing models, including Diamond OA, has the potential to change with the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA), a movement with more than 7800 signatories in December 2024 (CoARA, 2024). A change in research culture could indeed also emphasise the value of the essential community work that Diamond OA editors perform. Furthermore, institutions leading the international movement for reforming research assessment strive to move away from narrow quantitative metrics, such as the Journal Impact Factor (JIF), while recognizing and rewarding the diversity, quality and openness of contributions to science and society. Whereas the JIF prioritises articles in journals indexed in exclusive paywalled databases, the Diamond OA ecosystem provides a platform and open indexation for the range of inclusive and diverse research contributions.

It is important to recognise that these reasons for supporting Diamond OA are interrelated and complementary, each reinforcing the other. For example, cultural and social motivations become more effective when paired with economic and financial considerations. Conversely, economic and financial considerations need guidance from cultural and social motivations. Top-down and bottom-up support from governments and research communities equally enhance the effectiveness and guidance of other considerations, and will help solidify quality scholar-led publishing in the future.

4.0 Typologies

The DIAMAS landscape study of 685 institutional publishers and publishing service providers in the ERA (Armengou et al., 2023) identified that many of these publishers were publishing journals, books and other outputs via Diamond OA. For this report, we have further interpreted the data to identify four 'user types', which describe, in general terms, the types of publishing operations that might be identified by a parent organisation. The parent organisations can generally be described as RPOs or departments of such, and learned societies and associations.

4.1 Institutional publishers operating independently but under the control of a parent organisation

These publishing operations are organised as separate organisations under the control of the parent, which can take different forms. These publishers are more financially

independent of their parents than the other groups. As separate entities, their costs are less likely to be covered by in-kind or monetary funding from the parents. They are less likely to provide any publishing services to others outside of their own parent organisation. They are also much less likely to publish books or grey literature.

Typically this category can describe university presses that are still under the control of the parent organisation.

4.2 Institutional publishers within an organisation

This category of publishing operations has three major types:

1. A department of the parent organisation
2. Part of a department of the parent organisation
3. Part of a library in the parent organisation

These publishing operations are all heavily dependent on financial resources from their parent organisation. They generally start the year with an approved budget. Those who are a department of the parent organisation generally seem to have better budgets than the others. They are larger publishers than the single, independent journals both in terms of the number of journals and in the size of the journals

Generally speaking, those that are departments or parts of departments are strongly rooted within a larger research community in the institution and are developing/have developed over time from traditional publishing activities.

Library-based publishing looks to be of a more recent date and not as well connected to other parts of the institution. Library publishers are generally smaller than other publishers in this category. Those who are part of a library look more favourably on collaborating with others to save costs, they also report having fewer full-time equivalent resources available than the others and being more dependent on non-monetary and in-kind support.

4.3 Single, independent journals within an organisation

A large and under-represented group (both in this and other surveys) are stand-alone journals located within, but not well connected to, a scholarly institution such as a university. These are characterised by being small in publishing volumes with a low number of articles. Their finances are often difficult, and they are also often highly dependent on one or a few key individuals and their capacity to donate work. Such IPs generally have problems living up to expected technical standards of publishing and

dissemination. On the other hand, these small IPs are often at the core of a scholarly community and important to many scholars in the relevant fields.

4.4 Institutional publishers that do not report having a parent organisation, do not know, or may be the parent organisation themselves

Among respondents that identified themselves as institutional publishers, about half report having a parent institutional organisation. However, nearly half report not having a parent, or not knowing if they have a parent. While this might seem paradoxical, some of this group include learned societies, small publishers or RPOs at the top level, e.g., some of these publishers could be described as being the parent of a learned society journal. This group could be described as a separate user type.

While it is difficult to properly interpret the absence of an IP's parent organisation: it may be that some enjoy independent financial support. However, this could also signify that there might be a lack of internal interest, support, or governance from the higher organisational level or a desire to maintain a distance from the parent organisation, for example, single, independent journals in the category above.

5.0 Key DIAMAS results and publications

In this section, we report on the key DIAMAS outputs, which underpin this report and the actionable recommendations (D6.2).

5.1 The Diamond OA Standard (DOAS)

The Diamond OA Standard (DOAS) (Consortium of the DIAMAS project, 2024a) is a cornerstone of the DIAMAS project. DOAS is focused on aligning quality and best practices across non-fee-based open access scholarly journals, more commonly known as Diamond OA. DOAS presents a two-level approach to compliance with its standards, distinguishing between required and desired elements. It meets a variety of institutional publishing demands, and contributes to enhancing the accessibility and quality of Diamond OA journals. The ultimate mission of DOAS is the advancement of science and scholarship. The quality parameters it puts forward should be viewed as a public good.

In support of institutional publishing and Diamond OA, DOAS can be used by key stakeholders² in a number of ways:

² While this list mentions stakeholders that are within the scope of analysis of the DIAMAS project, DOAS can also be an important resource for other actors in the scholarly communication system. These include reviewers and editors who can use DOAS to support their decision-making in the different phases of scholarly publishing.

- **Institutional leaders, directors of libraries, and learned societies** can encourage the Diamond OA publishers working within their organisations to use DOAS to evaluate their compliance with high-quality Diamond OA publishing standards.
- In addition, the resource is a guideline and a practical benchmarking tool, which can be used to assess the quality of Diamond OA publishing. **Funders, sponsors and donors** can use DOAS to ensure that money supports quality in scholarly communication and viable alternatives to commercial publishers.
- DOAS can also be an effective tool to support evidence-based **policy making** for Diamond OA. Ensuring that the seven core components of DOAS (see below) are addressed in policy will both support quality and help widespread adherence to the DOAS guidelines.

DOAS has been developed in different stages and derives from the Extensible Quality Standard for Institutional Publishing (EQSIP), a refined framework of quality standards that establishes a unified benchmark, prioritising quality, transparency, sustainability and equity. Developed through an iterative refinement process, EQSIP V1.0 integrated relevant standards from 71 documents, followed by a gap analysis. EQSIP V2.0 further refined the structure and content of V1.0 based on the feedback and the recommendations of the gap analysis, and including the co-creative input from various publishing communities across Europe. Eight focus groups and a public consultation process were taken into account in finalising [EQSIP V2.0](#), ensuring inclusivity and representativity. This collaborative effort allowed DOAS to evolve into a comprehensive standard for Diamond OA publishing in Europe and beyond, reflecting the diverse needs of Diamond OA publishers. The iterative approach adopted in its elaboration ensures DOAS adaptability and provides a good representation of evolving scholarly publishing practices.

The seven core components of DOAS are:

1. **Funding:** This component aims at ensuring a sustainable Diamond OA business model, editorial independence, and cost transparency.
2. **Governance:** The purpose of this component is to define and establish ownership and control by the scholarly community, transparent mission-driven strategic governance, and clear relations with service providers.
3. **Open Science practices:** This component promotes open science policies, authors' rights, intellectual property rights, licensing practices, and sharing via a repository.

4. Editorial management: This component emphasises the importance of strong independent editorial bodies, transparency in peer review, editorial quality processes, and research integrity.
5. Technical service efficiency: This component aims at ensuring strong publishing infrastructures, interoperability and metadata robustness, as well as appropriate collaboration and preservation strategies.
6. Visibility, communication, marketing, and impact: This component enhances the visibility, communication, dissemination, and impact of published content through indexing, communication through various channels, and the provision of comprehensive usage metrics.
7. Equity, diversity, inclusion, and belonging (EDIB), gender, and multilingualism: This component focuses on promoting EDIB policies and practices, and ensuring equal participation, accessibility, and multilingualism as key quality elements.

DOAS offers two levels of compliance with its standards, distinguishing between required and desired elements. The required elements are necessary to meet the quality standard, while the desired elements provide advanced recommendations aimed at further improving compliance with the quality standard. Through this framework, Diamond OA publishers can improve the quality and transparency of governance, processes and workflows in their journal publishing activities, ensuring a common standard of transparency, accessibility, and integrity in scholarly publishing practices across disciplines and regions. Ultimately, this effort to align publishing standards across Diamond OA publishers will benefit both the scholarly community and society at large.

5.2 Other key DIAMAS resources for supporting Diamond OA

Table 1 describes the DIAMAS project's main outputs and their relevance to key stakeholder groups covered in this report. All project outputs, sub outputs and resources are available via the [DIAMAS website](#) and the [DIAMAS Project Community](#) on Zenodo. Project content has also been adapted for the [European Diamond Capacity Hub Toolsuite](#).

DIAMAS Project Outputs	Stakeholder		
	Institutional Leaders	Funders, Sponsors, Donors	Policy makers
Towards an enhanced and aligned institutional publishing landscape in the ERA	This preliminary policy document calls for increased alignment in institutional publishing along several dimensions: (1) geographical (i.e. national, regional, and		

	global), (2) disciplines and epistemic traditions, and (3) types of stakeholders (institutions, publishers, service providers, scholarly societies, journal editors), to benefit the work of researchers and thus enable science to progress faster.		
<p><u>The European Landscape of Institutional Publishing</u></p> <p><i>The report summarises the results of a survey conducted with over 600 Institutional Publishers in the ERA.</i></p>	Its contents allow for a quick understanding of the European Landscape and will allow Institutional Leaders to grasp the scale and challenges of publishers in different regions. This knowledge can inform decision-making and be useful evidence to support Diamond.		
<p><u>IPSP Sustainability Research Report</u></p>	Understanding the sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers (IPSPs) constitutes a key step in the DIAMAS project. This research report has one main objective: to investigate what financial sustainability means for institutional publishing in Europe and the workforce involved in it.		
<p><u>IPSP Best Practices: Quality evaluation criteria, best practices, and assessment systems for Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs)</u></p> <p><i>This report outlines existing quality evaluation criteria, best practices, and assessment systems for IPSPs developed by international associations, RPOs, governments, and</i></p>	Its contents allow Institutional Leaders to have evidence of existing quality ^[R1] criteria that could fit their institutions' editorial services and improve their practices.		

<p><i>international databases. It also analyses academic literature on research evaluation of IPSPs, assessment criteria and indicators.</i></p>			
<p><u>DOAS Self assessment tool</u></p> <p><i>Designed to provide an intuitive user experience for Diamond OA publishers to analyse their level of compliance with the DOAS.</i></p>	<p>Upon completion, publishing operations within your institution can all use the self assessment tools to produce a final report, which evaluates compliance against DOAS. The report is confidential and can be repeated to generate new reports</p>		
<p><u>Diamond OA Sustainability Check</u></p> <p><i>To accompany DOAS, the sustainability check focuses on the financial health of publishers with guidelines and a practical self assessment tool.</i></p>	<p>Publishing from inside your institution should be financially healthy in order to offer viable and long-term alternatives to commercial publishers. The sustainability check is a great tool to help publishers understand their operations and plan for the future. The report is confidential and can be repeated to generate new reports</p>		
<p><u>National Overviews on Sustainability</u></p> <p><i>As both a full report and a factsheet, this deep dive into 10 national contexts shows unique conditions for Diamond OA. Diamond OA flourishes in countries with strong community leadership and public funding.</i></p>		<p>Evidence from the national overviews consistently shows that strong funding creates the right environment for Diamond OA. Using the responses in this report, we have provided a brief history of the to take a closer look at how this works in different contexts as you build a case to fund Diamond OA publishing.</p>	
<p><u>Talking points: Making the case to fund Diamond Open Access</u></p>	<p>This is a list of arguments for all those who have an interest in sustaining Diamond OA publishing, be they managers, institutional publishers or service providers, Open Access</p>	<p>This is a list of arguments for all those who have an interest in sustaining Diamond OA publishing, be they managers, institutional publishers or service providers, Open Access advocates or funders,</p>	

	advocates or funders, sponsors, or donors.	sponsors, or donors.	
Research funders committing to Diamond OA: A DIAMAS case study report		This report provides a set of insights into why and how research funders are trying to support Diamond OA publishing. It provides case studies examining different funders and their motivations and funding mechanisms, and what this means for their work.	
Optimise your expenses: Guide for Diamond Open Access publishers <i>This guide is designed to help Diamond Open Access publishers manage their expenses and save resources.</i>	It walks Diamond OA publishers through the typical costs involved in running a Diamond OA publishing project, with questions that encourage them to think about their current practices and explore ways to optimise costs.		

Table 1. DIAMAS project's main outputs and their relevance to key stakeholder groups covered in this report

6.0 Concluding remarks

In this report, we have first provided a brief overview of the efforts in the last five years to give more visibility to Diamond OA and outlined the various reasons to support Diamond OA as an alternative to commercial publishing. We have identified four Diamond OA publisher typologies, illustrating the challenges Diamond OA publishers face. Key DIAMAS project outputs are described. These resources will be made sustainable in the form of specific services in the European Diamond Capacity Hub (DIAMAS, 2025).

Diamond OA is gaining momentum across the world through the leadership of funders, infrastructures, institutional publishers, scholars, and projects, such as DIAMAS and ALMASI. For a sector with thousands of journals and a strong developing infrastructure that has organically grown over time, there is much hope for Diamond OA today. Efforts are scaling up to engage with institutional publishers and service providers, mobilising them to focus on quality and their sustainability for a stronger future, and nations are committing to Diamond OA by providing support for national initiatives, be they

organisational or technical. Diamond OA publishers have new good practices, tools and services to hand through national and international projects such as DIAMAS.

The future of Diamond OA depends on a range of stakeholders providing vital policy and financial frameworks to uphold this movement based on a growing international evidence-base. Governments, funding agencies, universities, scholarly societies, academic libraries, publishers, specific industrial sectors, and infrastructures need to help maintain and grow Diamond OA publishing. Informed, clear, and targeted policy recommendations will provide a compass to these stakeholders who seek to support scholar-led equitable pathways to OA. Continued and increased commitment through policy, incentives, financial, in-kind, and expert support will be key to ensure that we are able to make this more equitable OA system thrive.

The implementation of Diamond OA policy and practice is a joint responsibility of stakeholders. We believe that the synergetic outcomes from the DIAMAS project now need to be matched by equally synergetic support from institutional stakeholders for Diamond OA: the EU, European national policymakers, ministries, RFOs, RPOs, learned societies, and academic libraries, as well as with stakeholders outside of Europe to grow and strengthen Diamond OA on a global scale. Diamond OA publishers and editors are ready to do their part, it is time for institutional stakeholders to step up to the plate more forcefully to help us fill the gaps we have identified.

In the companion report, *Recommendations and Implementation Guidelines for Institutions, Funders, Sponsors, and Donors, and Policymakers* (10.5281/zenodo.14719790), we present a set of recommendations and implementation guidelines developed to help institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors (FSDs), and policymakers that support, or are willing to support, Diamond Open Access (OA) as a model for scholarly publishing.

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